

DIAMAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY OF ORGANO-METALLIC COMPOUNDS.
PART II. BISMUTH COMPOUNDS

BY N. K. PARAB AND D. M. DESAI

The diamagnetic susceptibilities of some organo-bismuth compounds, R_3Bi , and their dichlorides, R_3BiCl_2 , have been determined by a modified form of Gouy's method. The results show that the susceptibility of bismuth atom, deduced from trivalent and pentavalent compounds, differ by about 7 units. The difference observed in χ_M values from trivalent and pentavalent compounds may be due to the difference in the structure of these two types of compounds. The susceptibility of $\chi_{M^{3+}}$ and $\chi_{M^{5+}}$ have been theoretically calculated using Slater's and Angus' methods compared with χ_{Bi} values deduced from trivalent and pentavalent compounds.

In continuation of the work reported earlier (*this issue*, p. 569), the diamagnetic susceptibility of some organo-bismuth compounds of the type R_3Bi and R_3BiX_3 has been studied in this investigation. Only one compound, namely, triphenylbismuthine, has been studied so far (cf. Pascal, *Compt. rend.*, 1921, 173, 144, 1712; 1922, 174, 437, 1898; 1922, 175, 1963).

EXPERIMENTAL

The compounds studied in this investigation were prepared by the known methods and were purified by repeated crystallisations before measurements. Their melting points and the percentage metal contents were determined to establish their purity. In the case of dihalides, the close agreement between the observed and the reported melting points was taken as the criterion of purity, as those compounds were found difficult to decompose.

The diamagnetic susceptibility of these compounds were determined and calculated as reported in Part I (*loc. cit.*). The results of the susceptibility measurements are shown in Table I. These values are the mean of at least three independent determinations (in terms of -1×10^{-6} c.g.s. units).

TABLE I

No.	Compounds.	Formula.	χ_M .	χ_M .	χ_M .	χ_{Bi} .
1	Triphenylbismuthine	$(C_6H_5)_3Bi$	0.4422 ± 0.003	194.6	156.27	38.33
2	Tri- <i>p</i> -tolylbismuthine?	$[p\text{-}CH_3\text{-}C_6H_4]_3Bi$	0.4755 ± 0.003	229.2	191.85	37.35
3	Tri- <i>m</i> -xylylbismuthine	$[m\text{-}(CH_3)_2\text{-}C_6H_3]_3Bi$	0.5013 ± 0.003	262.7	227.43	35.27
4	Triphenylbismuthine dichloride	$(C_6H_5)_3BiCl_2$	0.4457 ± 0.003	227.7	196.47	31.23
5	Tri- <i>p</i> -tolylbismuthine dichloride	$(CH_3\text{-}C_6H_4)_3BiCl_2$	0.4764 ± 0.003	263.4	232.05	31.35
6	Tri- <i>m</i> -xylylbismuthine dichloride	$(CH_3)_2C_6H_3BiCl_2$	0.4983 ± 0.003	296.5	267.63	28.87

DISCUSSION

Only one compound, namely, triphenylbismuthine, was studied by Pascal (*loc. cit.*) who obtained the specific susceptibility value as -0.447×10^{-6} . The value obtained by us is in close agreement with this reported value.

Susceptibility of Tri- and Pentavalent Bismuth.—The triphenylbismuthine may be looked upon as the substitution product of H_3Bi which contains trivalent bismuth.

The susceptibility of trivalent bismuth has been deduced from the molar susceptibilities of triarylbi-muthines. Pascal's values (cf. Bhatnagar and Mathur, "Physical Principles and Applications of Magneto-chemistry", 1935, pp. 90-93) of various atoms and constitutive correction constants were used to calculate the susceptibility of the organic part of the molecule (χ_a). Triarylbi-muthine dihalides are the addition products obtained by adding two halogen atoms to the corresponding triaryl compound. These compounds therefore contain pentavalent bismuth atom. The susceptibility of pentavalent bismuth has been deduced from the molar susceptibilities of the triarylbi-muthine dichloride by using Pascal's values (*loc. cit.*) of various atoms other than bismuth and the relevant constitutive correction constants (χ_a). These values of trivalent and pentavalent bismuth atom, deduced from the corresponding compounds, are shown in the last column of Table I.

It will be seen that the susceptibility values of trivalent bismuth atom, deduced from the triarylbi-muthines, agree very closely with each other, the average value being found as -36.98×10^{-6} . This value represents the susceptibility of trivalent bismuth in compounds of the type R_3Bi . Similarly, it has been observed that the susceptibility of pentavalent bismuth atom, deduced from dichlorides, are very near each other, the average value being found as -30.48×10^{-6} , which represents the susceptibility of pentavalent bismuth atom in compounds of the type R_3BiX_2 . It is obvious that these values of tri- and pentavalent bismuth atom are inclusive of the bond effects due to C—Bi and Bi—halogen linkages, as the case may be.

It will be seen, on comparison, that the susceptibility of trivalent bismuth atom, deduced from triarylbi-muthines, is lower than that of pentavalent bismuth atom, deduced from dihalides, by about 7.0 units. A similar difference was also observed in the susceptibility value of antimony in trivalent and pentavalent compounds of the type R_3Sb and R_3SbX_2 . These results therefore support the observation of Kido (cf. Part I, *loc. cit.*). The observed difference in the susceptibility of bismuth atom in these two types of compounds may possibly be due to the difference in the structure of these compounds. Bergmann and Schutz (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1932, **B19**, 401) have studied the dipole moment of triphenylbismuthine and from the zero value of dipole moment of this compound, they have concluded that its structure is that of a plane triangle with bismuth atom situated at the centre of gravity. The addition of two halogen atoms to the triarylbi-muthine changes the covalency of bismuth from 3 to 5 and like the dihalides of triarylstibines, the triarylbi-muthine dichloride may have a trigonal bipyramidal structure. Jenson (*Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1943, **250**, 257) observed that the molecular polarisation of triphenylbismuthine dichloride was in-

dependent of temperature. It has accordingly a zero dipole moment which shows that the molecule possesses the configuration of a trigonal bipyramid. The large atomic polarisation in this compound also indicates that the binding between the central atom and the halogen atom is strongly polar. The halogens in R_3BiX_2 compounds have also been found to be quite labile and undergo double decomposition readily (cf. Gillinan and Yale, *Chem. Rev.*, 1942, 30, 304). All these evidences show that bismuth has a greater positive charge in the dihalides than in triaryl compounds. It is obvious therefore that as a consequence of the greater positive charge on the bismuth atom in dihalides, χ_{Bi} values would be smaller in these compounds than in triaryl compounds.

Comparison of Observed χ_{Bi} with the Theoretically Calculated Values.—The susceptibility values of Bi^{3+} and Bi^{5+} have been calculated by using Slater's (*Phys. Rev.*, 1930, 36, 57) and Angus' (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1932, 136A, 569) methods and these theoretically calculated values together with the values deduced from trivalent and pentavalent compounds are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

	$\chi_{Bi^{3+}}$ values.		
	Obs.	Calc.	
		Slater.	Angus.
Trivalent	36.98	41.35	41.29
Pentavalent	30.48	28.74	28.68

It is observed that χ_{Bi} value, deduced from trivalent compounds, is lower than the theoretically calculated value by about 5 units, while that obtained from pentavalent compounds is in good agreement with the calculated values. The theoretical values are for free Bi^{3+} and Bi^{5+} ions. In the triaryl bismuthine, the link between Bi—C will be essentially covalent, although it may have a certain ionic character. The difference in the electronegativities of Bi and C will be greater than that in the case of Sb and C. The departure of the theoretically calculated $\chi_{Bi^{3+}}$ values from the value deduced from trivalent compounds may thus be due to the formation of Bi—C links. It is found that χ_{Bi} value obtained from pentavalent bismuth compounds agrees more closely with the calculated value for Bi^{5+} , using Slater's and Angus' methods, than the corresponding value for $\chi_{Sb^{5+}}$ agrees with $\chi_{Sb^{5+}}$, calculated by these methods. This may be due to the greater ionic character of Bi—C and Bi—Cl linkages as compared with the Sb—C and Sb—Cl linkages.

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